

Ceric—Cerium Oxidation of Catechol

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Ceric-cerium and catechol have been found to form complex which has got maximum absorbance at $\lambda_{\max}$ 440 m μ . The first order rate law follows the decomposition of the complex, yielding products through free radical.

The rate of the reaction is retarded by increasing cerium(III) and sulphuric acid concentrations. The thermodynamics parameters in dynamics of the oxidation process have been evaluated.

THOUGH the oxidation of phenol and substituted phenols are instantaneous and simple¹, the mechanisms of such oxidation process are not the same. The reaction mechanism even with the same oxidant is complicated and controversial²⁻⁴. The complexity in the mechanism can be well judged by varied complicated oxidation products in such oxidation process with different oxidants⁵⁻¹⁴. It is surprising that a study on the mode of oxidation of phenol and substituted phenols by strong oxidant like ceric-cerium is lacking.

The variation of oxidising power of ceric-cerium in sulphuric acid is the least, [as the redox potential Ce(IV)/Ce(III) varies from 1.44 volt to 1.42 volt if the acid concentration is varied from 1N to 8N] whereas the variation is large in other acids.

The species of ceric-cerium in sulphuric acid of known concentration are well defined¹⁵ and slight variation in the experimental conditions will not markedly affect the oxidising power of the oxidant. This paper describes the experimental results in the oxidation of catechol by ceric-cerium.

Experimental

Materials: The chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Triple distilled water was used throughout the investigation.

Kinetic measurements: Ceric ammonium sulphate dissolved in known concentration of sulphuric acid and catechol dissolved in known concentration of acetic acid were brought to the same desired temperature and then rapidly mixed in a bottle previously thermostated to the same temperature. The kinetics of the reaction were followed by withdrawing a known volume of the reaction mixture at definite interval of time, into ice-cold water to quench the reaction velocity. The unchanged ceric-ion was quickly estimated with standard Mohr's salt solution using ferroin-as an indicator.

Stoichiometry and product analysis: The reaction mixture containing a known excess of ceric-cerium over the organic substrate was kept overnight. The unreacted oxidant was estimated. Orthobenzoquinone was found to be the ultimate oxidation product. It was identified by centrifuging the reaction mixture. The centrifugate was thoroughly shaken with excess of ether, for two to three hours. The ethereal layer was separated and was kept for few hours when colourless crystals, having light red tinge separated out [m.p. 74°].

The experimental results ($\Delta[\text{Ce(IV)}]/\Delta$ organic substrate) lead to the following equation:

Test for organic free radical: The reaction mixture was flushed with nitrogen to expel oxygen from the system and then methyl-methacrylate was added. The onset of polymerisation was indicated by the appearance of turbidity in the initially clear solution. The turbidity increased with the progress of polymerisation¹⁶.

Results and Discussion

The results of ceric-cerium oxidation of catechol are presented in Table 1. It was observed that the rate becomes kinetically immeasurable if attempt is made to deviate from the given concentration of either oxidant or organic substrate.

TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON Ce(IV) IN 1.0 M SULPHURIC ACID AND CATECHOL IN 30% HOAC AT 35°

[Ce(IV)] × 10 ⁴ M	[Catechol] × 10 ⁴ M	10 ³ K ₁ min ⁻¹
1.00	8.88	6.84 ± 0.03
1.00	7.69	5.30 ± 0.08
1.00	7.14	3.96 ± 0.08
1.00	6.66	2.94 ± 0.04
0.954	7.14	5.12 ± 0.05
0.909	7.14	5.52 ± 0.08
0.869	7.14	6.32 ± 0.02

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The significant retarding effect of Ce(III) was observed which was more pronounced in lower concentration of organic substrate and higher concentration of oxidant. This was further confirmed by performing separate experiment in which cerous salt was added from outside. The duplicate rate measurements were found to be reproducible within $\pm 2\%$.

Effect of temperature on rate constant: The Arrhenius law was found to be valid. The values of thermodynamic parameter are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON RATE CONSTANT

Temp A°	$10^3 K_1 \text{ min}^{-1}$	ΔS e.u.	$PZ \times 10^7$ min ⁻¹	ΔH K.cals/ mols	ΔF K.cals/ mols	ΔE K.cals/ mols
298	1.30 ± 0.03	-25.48	1.832	11.971	20.16	
303	1.78 ± 0.01	-25.57	1.776	11.961	20.31	12.567
308	2.96 ± 0.03	-25.71	2.100	11.951	20.33	(mean)
313	3.83 ± 0.01	-25.43	1.973	11.941	20.51	

Inhibiting effect of sulphuric acid: The rate of reaction was found to decrease on increasing the sulphuric acid concentration, Table 3.

TABLE 3—RATE DEPENDENCE ON SULPHURIC ACID CONCENTRATION

$[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4](M)$;	$10^3 K_1(\text{min}^{-1})$;	1.50	1.00	0.500	0.25
$10^4 [\text{Catechol}] = 7.14M$; $[\text{HOAC}] = 30\%(\text{v/v})$;	2.15 ± 0.02	2.96 ± 0.03	4.46 ± 0.02	5.54 ± 0.02	
$10^3 [\text{Ce(IV)}] = 1.0M$ Temp = 35.0°					

It appears that the inhibiting effect observed was due to the formation of the species ${}^1\text{H Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_3^-$.

Effect of acetic acid concentration on rate constant: The value of rate constant increases on increasing % composition of acetic acid, Table 4.

TABLE 4—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON ACETIC ACID CONCENTRATION

% of water HOAC (v/v)	30	40	50	60
$10^3 [\text{Ce(IV)}] = 1.0M$; $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.0M$;	2.96 ± 0.03	3.34 ± 0.02	3.82 ± 0.02	4.84 ± 0.02
$10^4 [\text{Catechol}] = 7.14M$ Temp = 35.0°				

This observation may indicate the increase in protonation which suppresses the formation of bisulphate ion, responsible for removing active oxidant species from the reaction field.

Salt effect on reaction rate: Varying concentrations of sulphate of sodium and ammonium were found to exert no effect on reaction rate.

When oxidant and organic substrate were mixed together, a beautiful light red colour developed immediately. This had maximum optical density of 0.40 while the light yellow colour of oxidant had optical density of 0.16 at λ 440 m μ . This colouration was found to fade away slowly.

All the experimental observations recorded lead to the fact that the reaction proceeds through complex formation which slowly decomposes to give the reaction products through free radical.

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